

Sympatric Speciation: Mechanisms and Proofs

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Introduction

Sympatric speciation refers to the occurrence of speciation in a population despite the absence of geographical divisions (Foote, 2018). As a result of the long history of debate within the field of theoretical evolutionary biology, there is now a consensus among researchers that sympatric speciation is plausible given the presence of specific parameters (Martin et al., 2013). However, the validity of sympatric speciation remains contentious as researchers attempting to validate sympatric speciation via collecting data in nature often use definitions that are most congruent with their data (Gavrilets, 2014). In response, to strengthen the validity of sympatric speciation, the underlying theory and proofs supporting sympatric speciation will be outlined and consolidated. The following discussion will synthesise the findings of the primary scientific literature concerning the mechanisms of sympatric speciation including reasons as to why sympatric speciation is less likely than allopatric speciation, and the myriad examples of sympatric speciation occurring in nature.

Mechanisms for Sympatric Speciation

Gavrilets (2014) argues that the conclusions from a half-century long debate regarding the conditions necessary to achieve sympatric speciation are that sympatric speciation only occurs if there is disruptive selection, unrestricted assortative mating, and elevated genetic variation at the beginning of disruptive selection. According to da Silva (2017) and Brown (2016) the current understanding of disruptive selection is hinged upon mathematical game theory, the

study of how an individual's survival strategy is informed by the strategy of other individuals within the population. In general, disruptive selection occurs if different survival strategies and their respective phenotypes are effective for survival and are thus selected for; this creates a bimodal distribution which can lead to speciation (Brown, 2016). In addition, Jiang, Bolnick and Kirkpatrick (2013) contend that assortative mating results in reproductive isolation and, consequently, speciation. Assortative mating is ultimately caused by the selection for heritable phenotype matching behaviours that confer higher fitness to individuals; behaviours, for instance, that favour the presence of fit phenotypes in the offspring (Servedio, 2015). Lastly, Martin et al. (2013) suggests that gene flow between species in sympatry creates genetic diversity which can then be a starting point for disruptive selection to create a bimodal distribution of genotypes and phenotypes.

Newer research continues to build on and support these conclusions. For instance, Rettelbach et al. (2013) proposes that two accepted mechanisms of sympatric speciation, ecological niche specialisation, how two subpopulations adapted to two specific ecological niches are individually selected for, and frequency-dependent selection, the dependency of phenotype fitness on phenotype frequency, can work in a step-wise manner, as opposed to the common view that the presence of one negates the presence of the other, and cause sympatric speciation faster than if either mechanism were to operate in isolation. Moreover, Friedman, Alm and Shapiro (2013) revive, prove using a bacterial population, and stress the importance of an older theoretical claim that sympatric speciation can only occur if only a small number of loci code for the trait being selected as recombination can dampen the magnitude of disruptive selection. Furthermore, Linksvayer, Busch and Smith (2013) argue that social factors such as the development of certain parasitic practices can also facilitate sympatric speciation. A prime example of this claim is the emergence of ant social parasites that appear as queen ants but are incapable of producing worker ants and instead use worker ants from a

phenotypically related species to support their development (Linksvayer, Busch & Smith, 2013). This claim is supported by Rabeling et al. (2014) who sequenced the mitochondrial and nuclear DNA of a sympatric population of ant social parasites to prove that ant social parasites, “cheater queens,” speciated from the host species and not allopatrically from related species.

Reasons for Allopatric Speciation being more common than Sympatric Speciation

The primary reason as to why allopatric speciation is typically viewed as more common than sympatric speciation is because of the gene flow that continues to occur in populations existing in sympatry (Papadopulos, Baker, & Savolainen, 2013). Papadopulos, Baker and Savolainen (2013) state that allopatry, the geographical division of two populations, supposedly removes the factor of gene flow and thus ensures that genetic mutation and drift lead to reproductive isolation and, with enough genetic divergence, speciation. This is directly supported by the aforementioned idea that the presence of recombination, as is expected in a population unseparated by geographical divisions, dampens the magnitude of disruptive selection, a prerequisite to sympatric speciation (Friedman, Alm, & Shapiro, 2013). On a related note, Bowen et al. (2013) state that sympatric speciation may occur faster than allopatric speciation because disruptive selection initiates reproductive isolation faster compared to the mutation and genetic drift that allopatric speciation relies on.

Interestingly, there is still dissent regarding the extent to which allopatric speciation is more widespread than sympatric speciation. For instance, Yang et al. (2017) state that the overwhelmingly large number of neutral genes that have no direct effect on the fitness of individuals may allow genes that confer higher fitness to remain relatively unperturbed by gene flow. Both Yang et al. (2017) and Papadopulos, Baker and Savolainen (2013) agree that the true prevalence of the occurrence of sympatric speciation in nature remains to be elucidated as

current methods such as genome sequencing and phylogenetic analyses are unable to fully measure and understand the behaviour-driven processes underlying most cases of sympatric speciation. Additionally, Hadid et al. (2013) postulate that sympatric speciation may be more common in nature than previously believed because of the prevalence of different ecological niches within a single geographical area. Therefore, the endemicity of allopatric speciation relative to the endemicity of sympatric speciation remains to be accurately measured.

Proof of Sympatric Speciation

Many studies have found examples of sympatric evolution that directly enforce the validity of proposed theories of the mechanisms and characteristics of sympatric speciation. Bowen et al. (2013) state that there are a myriad examples in tropical marine life that exemplify sympatric speciation. For instance, Caribbean and East Pacific reef fish demonstrate a unique mechanism for reproductive isolation via assortative mating by calling potential mates using vocal calls in the dark (Bowen et al., 2013). Hadid et al. (2013) maintains that two different species of blind mole rats (*Spalax*) diverged from an ancestral population through sympatric speciation due to adaptation to two different types of soil (i.e. by ecological niche specialisation, an idea mentioned in the mechanisms section). There are also attempts to apply models of sympatric speciation to understand the modes of speciation of species that are not sexual eukaryotes. For example, Ho et al. (2016) demonstrates using phylogenies constructed using genome sequences of different plant viruses that elderberry carlaviruses, a plant virus strain that causes disease in elderberries, arose within the “geographical limitations” of the elderberry (i.e. no gene flow from viruses of other fruit species). Moreover, Leuven et al. (2014) demonstrates that sympatry was required to cause a specific speciation event in bacteria within a host (e.g. the

“geographical limitation”) as the two new genotypes that arose were dependent on each other to function.

However, several researchers still call for vigilance in being too rash when using examples to validate theories and the endemism of sympatric speciation. For instance, Foote (2018) argues that the widely celebrated example of supposed sympatric speciation observed in Cameroon crater lake cichlids is disproved as genome sequencing shows that the speciation occurred with allopatry (i.e. because there was evidence of “multiple colonisations” and “secondary gene flow”). In addition, Wolf and Ellegren (2017) argue that recent research applying genome sequencing to sympatric speciation is riddled with biases favouring the occurrence of adaptation and as a result, misinterpretations of data. Wolf and Ellegren (2017) call for an increase in “re-analysis and re-interpretation” of published data within the field of evolutionary genomics, particularly with respect to genomics applied to understand sympatric speciation.

Conclusion

The reasons underlying the occurrence of sympatric speciation were outlined, the prevailing rationale behind why allopatric speciation is the dominant mode of speciation was stated, and several case studies were listed to serve as evidence for sympatric speciation. A common thread that ran through this discussion is that sympatric speciation was and continues to be a contentious topic, especially with regards to its true mechanisms in nature and its true endemism. As a next step, Gavrillets (2014) suggests that empiricists and theorists alike need to evaluate how best to construct a single accepted definition of sympatric evolution to facilitate coherence among future empirical studies investigating sympatric speciation in nature. Furthermore, Foote (2018) contends that the rise of genomic sequencing coupled with

phylogenetic analyses in determining the occurrence of sympatric speciation within a population has shown that certain conditions for sympatric speciation proposed by theoreticians are not always applicable in nature, and thus researchers should continue to use a genic approach to confirm or disprove the validity of long-standing theories. In sum, the controversy surrounding sympatric speciation can only be solved if best practices and new approaches that attempt to validate proposed theories with accurate empirical data are employed.

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